

Real-World Utilization, Outcomes, and Safety of Pre-Prescribed Emergency Medication Kits

Nicolas Hulscher, MPH^{1, 2*}, James A. Thorp, MD², Drew Pinsky, MD², Peter Gillooly, MSc², Foster Coulson², Melissa Annazone², Chloe Radesi², Jessica Brooks², Harvey Risch, MD, PhD^{2, 3}, Peter A. McCullough, MD, MPH^{1, 2} Kelly Victory, MD²

¹McCullough Foundation, Dallas, TX

²The Wellness Company, Boca Raton, FL

³Yale School of Public Health, New Haven, CT

***Correspondence:** nichulscher@gmail.com

Abstract

Background: Direct-to-consumer (DTC) prescribed emergency medication kits provide households with a set of pre-prescribed medications for future use, but no real-world utilization data on this product category have been published.

Methods: We conducted a cross-sectional online survey of verified purchasers of an eight-medication prescribed kit (506 respondents). We describe utilization, self-reported outcomes among intended-use episodes (medication taken by the prescribed recipient), safety signals, free-text themes, and rural–urban distribution. Proportions carry 95% Wilson confidence intervals.

Results: Respondents were predominantly older adults (mean age 65.1 years; 77% aged 60 or over), and 75% resided in metropolitan ZIP codes. Of 506 respondents, 487 (96.4% of the 505 answering) had opened the kit and 364 (71.9%) had used it at least once. Repeat use was common, with 143 (28.3%) using it three or more times, and 114/367 (31.1%) of use-reporting respondents used it while traveling or in a remote setting. Among respondents describing a specific episode, the time from kit receipt to that use was within one month for 17 (4.6%), within three months for 82 (22.3%), within six months for 110 (30.0%), within one year for 120 (32.7%), and more than one year for 38 (10.4%). Respiratory illness accounted for 218/367 (59.4%) of described episodes. Among 333 intended-use episodes, 81.6% (95% CI 77.1–85.4) reported meaningful improvement within three days, 51.8% (46.4–57.1) perceived a reduced need for urgent care or the emergency department, and 86.1% (82.0–89.4) avoided clinic, urgent care, or hospital visitation. Overall self-reported net benefit was 95.8% (318/332; 95% CI 93.0–97.5; any positive perceived difference: reduced urgent-care/ED need, reduced disruption, or helped manage until care was available). Care escalation within 7 days occurred after 20/368 use-reporting respondents' episodes (5.4%). Side effects were reported in 8/332 intended-use episodes (2.4%), all mild.

Conclusions: In the first real-world data on DTC emergency medication kits with pre-prescribed medications, respondents reported high engagement, frequent use for common acute illness, rapid symptom resolution, infrequent and mild side effects, and preparedness benefits extending even to never-users. These findings suggest that pre-prescribed emergency medication kits may represent a practical model for improving timely access to treatment and guided self-management of common acute illness when conventional access is limited or inconvenient. Large prospective, randomized trials are warranted in willing populations at risk for common illnesses covered in the kits.

Keywords: self-treatment; medication kit; direct-to-consumer; health care access; preparedness; patient experience

1. Introduction

Timely access to prescription treatment for common acute illnesses remains uneven in the United States. Older adults face disproportionate burdens from clinic wait times and infectious exposure in waiting rooms. Rural residents and others with limited access to healthcare services may face significant barriers to obtaining timely prescription treatment for acute illnesses. For many acute infectious diseases, earlier initiation of appropriate treatment is associated with improved clinical outcomes and reduced morbidity and mortality [1–3].

The importance of early antibiotic treatment for prevention of sepsis related morbidity and mortality is clear. Analysis of CDC WONDER data from 1999–2022 found more than 4.1 million sepsis-related deaths in the United States and reported that mortality increased across most demographic and geographic groups during the study period [4]. These pressures are well documented: rural communities have lost hospitals at an accelerating pace over the past two decades, with measurable consequences for access to acute care among the older adults who disproportionately remain in those communities [5]. Community pharmacies have followed a similar trajectory: roughly one in eight US pharmacies closed between 2009 and 2015, closures have since outpaced openings, and pharmacy loss measurably reduces older adults' adherence to prescribed medication [6–8]. In the travel-medicine setting, the practice of equipping patients in advance with standby antibiotic therapy for self-treatment of travelers' diarrhea is well established and guideline-endorsed, with written self-treatment instructions considered a core component of pre-travel care [9,10]. The greatest limitation to guidelines-driven clinical effectiveness is availability of medication at the onset of illness.

Direct-to-consumer (DTC) prescribed emergency medication kits extend this standby-treatment concept beyond travel: a clinician reviews the purchaser's medical history and prescribes a fixed set of essential medications prophylactically to a named individual, dispensing the kit for storage at home so that treatment is available at the onset of illness. This reflects the broader principle of using essential medications prescribed prophylactically to avert negative health outcomes when timely access to care is uncertain. Despite growing consumer uptake of this product category, to our knowledge, no real-world data on how such kits are actually used have been published regarding how often, for what conditions, with what self-reported results, and with what fidelity to labeled directions. Prospective purchasers and clinicians currently lack utilization data to guide counseling, and the public-health community has little empirical insight into how households actually use prescribed medications kept on hand for future need. This is a timely question: even within conventional care, prescribing patterns for common infections remain an active area of study [11,12], and antibiotics are already commonly obtained without a prescription and stored for later use in the United States [13].

The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) does not regulate individual prescriptions issued by telemedicine doctors for direct-to-consumer medical emergency kits, as "pre-prescribing" medications in anticipation of a crisis falls under the standard practice of medicine. Licensed telemedicine physicians can leverage their autonomy to prescribe approved medications for emergency preparedness. To comply with federal laws like the Ryan Haight Act and state-level patient-relationship rules, The Wellness Company utilizes a digital health platform to conduct virtual patient evaluations before a pharmacy dispenses the

kit. Furthermore, the detailed clinical guidebooks and 24/7 telehealth backup included with these kits act as a necessary layer of medical oversight, ensuring that patients have immediate professional guidance to safely confirm a diagnosis before consuming any pre-prescribed emergency drugs.

We conducted a cross-sectional survey of verified purchasers of one widely distributed DTC kit. The objectives were to characterize (a) engagement and utilization patterns; (b) self-reported outcomes among episodes in which the kit was used as intended (medication taken by the prescribed recipient); and (c) safety signals, including side effects and use outside labeled directions.

2. Methods

2.1 The Medical Emergency Kit

The Medical Emergency Kit (The Wellness Company, USA) is a direct-to-consumer kit of eight prescription medications intended for adults aged 18 years and older. Following purchase, each recipient completes a medical history questionnaire reviewed by a licensed U.S. provider. A telemedicine consult is then conducted per state laws before prescribing to the patient. Medications may be omitted on the basis of reported allergies and medical history, and the prescription is issued to a single named individual and dispensed by a U.S. pharmacy. The kit includes a printed guidebook describing indications and directions for each medication, access to telehealth consultation, and medication replenishment for up to two years after purchase. Kit contents are listed in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Kit contents at the time of the survey.

Medication	Strength / quantity	Class
Amoxicillin-clavulanate	875 mg, 28 tablets	β -lactam/ β -lactamase-inhibitor antibiotic
Azithromycin	250 mg, 12 tablets	Macrolide antibiotic
Doxycycline	100 mg, 50 capsules	Tetracycline antibiotic
Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole	800/160 mg, 28 tablets	Sulfonamide combination antibiotic
Metronidazole	500 mg, 30 tablets	Nitroimidazole antibiotic/antiprotozoal
Ivermectin	12 mg, 25 compounded capsules	Antiparasitic
Fluconazole	150 mg, 2 tablets	Azole antifungal
Ondansetron	4 mg tablets	5-HT ₃ antagonist antiemetic

Kit also includes a printed guidebook, telehealth consultation access, and replenishment eligibility for up to two years.

2.2 Design, sampling frame, and response fraction

We conducted an online survey (Jotform) of verified kit purchasers, with responses collected through 8 June 2026. Survey invitations were delivered to 5,525 eligible purchasers identified through company distribution records. All invited purchasers acquired their kits in April 2025, providing approximately one year to encounter kit use-case scenarios between purchase and administration. A total of 513 submissions were received. After removal of duplicate submissions, 506 unique respondents formed the analytic sample (response fraction 9.2%; 506/5,525 delivered invitations). All respondents acknowledged a participation statement before completing the survey.

2.3 Data cleaning

Of 513 submissions received, 7 duplicate submissions (identified by respondent email address) were removed, retaining each respondent's most recent submission. Logically inconsistent usage counts ($n = 5$ records) and one malformed age value were set to missing without imputation. The dataset was de-identified prior to analysis.

2.4 Geographic classification (rural–urban)

Respondent ZIP codes were obtained from the customer sampling frame via a confidential linkage key (ZIP codes from one weekly export were repaired for stripped leading zeros). Each ZIP was classified using Rural-Urban Commuting Area (RUCA) ZIP-level codes (WWAMI Rural Health Research Center ZIP approximation [14]; primary codes 1–3 = metropolitan, 4–6 = micropolitan, 7–9 = small town, 10 = rural). Twenty respondent ZIP codes (4.0%) were not present in the crosswalk (predominantly ZIP codes created after the crosswalk vintage) and were treated as missing. Raw ZIP codes were discarded after classification, and only the derived category entered the analysis dataset. RUCA classifies the residential ZIP, while use during travel or in remote settings is captured separately by the survey travel item.

2.5 Statistical analysis

Categorical variables are reported as counts and percentages with 95% Wilson score confidence intervals for key proportions [15]. The Net Promoter Score (NPS) [16] is reported with a nonparametric bootstrap 95% confidence interval (2,000 resamples). The medication item was multi-select and is analyzed as episode-mentions. Primary outcome analyses (time to improvement, perceived difference, subsequent care, missed days, side effects) were restricted to intended-use episodes, defined as episodes in which the prescribed recipient used the medication ($n = 333$), and a sensitivity analysis repeated outcome calculations on all medication episodes. A post hoc composite of overall self-reported net benefit was defined among intended-use episodes as selection of any positive option on the perceived-difference item (reduced urgent-care/ED need, reduced disruption to daily life, or help managing until care was available). A stricter version additionally required meaningful improvement within 7 days and no reported side effect. Both are descriptive, perception-based summaries and are labeled post hoc. Analyses were performed in Python version 3.12 (Python Software Foundation) using the pandas, SciPy, and statsmodels libraries.

Pre-specified comparisons (chi-square statistic, or Fisher's exact statistic where expected cell counts were small) were: guidebook engagement \times composite deviation; age group (≥ 60 vs < 60 years) and symptom severity \times time-to-improvement and care-seeking; and rurality (metropolitan vs non-metropolitan) \times utilization and perceived urgent-care/emergency-department (ED) substitution, with the travel-use item as a consistency check. One exploratory logistic regression modeled perceived urgent-care/ED substitution on age group, severity, respiratory (vs other) condition, and guidebook engagement. No adjustment was made for multiple comparisons, and pre-specified and exploratory analyses are labeled as such. Complete-case analysis was used throughout. An exploratory, perception-based cost-offset scenario analysis is described in section 3.8 and relies on published per-visit cost benchmarks [17–20]. It is illustrative only.

2.6 Free-text analysis

Responses to the open-ended item were analyzed by software-assisted content analysis. All comments were read in full, a coding frame was developed inductively from the data, and keyword-based candidate coding was applied, with every impact-related assignment manually adjudicated by one investigator. The frame included a perceived-impact family applied only where the commenter made the statement explicitly (perceived avoidance of urgent care/ED/hospitalization; colloquial “lifesaver” language; perceived rapid recovery; perceived cost avoidance; access when conventional care was unavailable), broader experience themes, and deliberate convergence codes (expiration concerns; indication/dosing confusion). Participant quotations were edited minimally for brevity and to remove potentially identifying information while preserving the original meaning and intent.

3. Results

3.1 Participant flow

Figure 1 summarizes participant flow. Of 5,525 consecutive delivered invitations, 513 submissions were received and 506 unique respondents were analyzed. Of these, 364 (71.9%) had used the kit at least once and 367 described a specific use episode. A prescription medication from the kit was involved in 356 of those episodes, and the 333 episodes in which the prescribed recipient used the medication make up the intended-use outcome set. Respondents who never used the kit (n = 139) remain in all whole-sample analyses.

Figure 1. Participant flow.

3.2 Respondents and representativeness

Respondent characteristics are shown in **Table 2**. Mean age was 65.1 years (SD 10.1; median 66), and 390/505 (77.2%) were aged 60 years or older. Most purchased the kit for themselves (352, 69.6%) or their household (149, 29.4%). Among the 486 respondents with classifiable ZIP codes, 365 (75.1%) resided in metropolitan areas, 65 (13.4%) micropolitan, 32 (6.6%) small town, and 24 (4.9%) rural — 121 (24.9%) non-metropolitan overall.

Compared with non-responding adults in the frame, responders were similar in sex distribution (57.4% vs 55.3% female; $p = 0.39$), state distribution ($p = 0.056$), and rurality ($p = 0.83$), supporting representativeness on these measured characteristics (**Supplementary Table 1**), but were modestly older (mean 65.1 vs 62.4 years; standardized mean difference 0.23; $p < 0.001$)

Table 2. Respondent characteristics (n = 506).

Characteristic	n (%)
Age \geq 60 years (n=505 with age data)	390 (77.2%)
Purchased for self (primary user)	352 (69.6%)
Purchased for household	149 (29.4%)
Bachelor's degree or higher	284 (56.1%)
Household income \geq \$75,000	355 (70.2%)
Never smoker	352 (69.6%)
Alcohol less than weekly or never	391 (77.3%)
Diabetes or prediabetes diagnosis	75 (14.8%)
Metropolitan residence (n=486 classified)	365 (75.1%)
Non-metropolitan residence (n=486 classified)	121 (24.9%)

3.3 Engagement and utilization

Engagement was nearly universal: 487/505 (96.4%; 95% CI 94.4–97.7) had opened the kit and 494/506 (97.6%) had read most of (351, 69.4%) or skimmed (143, 28.3%) the guidebook. In total, 364 (71.9%) had used the kit at least once, and 143 (28.3%; 95% CI 24.5–32.3) had used it three or more times. Kits were stored most often in a home medicine cabinet (258, 51.0%) or a household emergency kit/go-bag (140, 27.7%). Among the 367 respondents answering the travel item, 114 (31.1%; 26.5–36.0) had used the kit at least once while traveling or in a remote setting. Most respondents (414, 81.8%) correctly identified that the kit is intended for the adult to whom it was prescribed, while 84 (16.6%) believed any household adult may use it and 8 (1.6%) were unsure (**Table 3**).

Table 3. Engagement and utilization (n = 506).

Characteristic	n (%)
Opened the kit (n=505)	487 (96.4%)
Read most of the guidebook	351 (69.4%)
Skimmed the guidebook	143 (28.3%)
Used the kit \geq 1 time	364 (71.9%)

Used 3+ times	143 (28.3%)
Used 5+ times	39 (7.7%)
Stored in home medicine cabinet	258 (51.0%)
Stored in emergency kit / go-bag	140 (27.7%)
≥1 use while traveling/remote (n=367)	114 (31.1%)
Correct understanding of intended user	414 (81.8%)

Travel-use percentage uses respondents answering that item (n = 367); opened-kit percentage uses n = 505.

3.4 Episode characteristics

Among 367 described episodes, respiratory illness was the most common concern (218, 59.4%), followed by urinary symptoms (55, 15.0%) and gastrointestinal illness (23, 6.3%). Most episodes occurred at home (287, 78.2%), with another 76 (20.7%) occurring during domestic or international travel or in a remote area. Severity was most often moderate (235, 64.0%), and 54 (14.7%) rated their symptoms severe or very severe. The most common first action was consulting the kit guidebook (247, 67.3%). Another 92 respondents (25.1%) used a medication first, and 290 (79.0%) did not contact a clinician at any point during the episode. Medication episode-mentions were led by amoxicillin-clavulanate (146), azithromycin (126), and ivermectin (92) (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2. Episode characteristics. (A) Primary health concern. (B) Medications used (episode-mentions; multi-select).

3.5 Self-reported outcomes among intended-use episodes

Among 333 intended-use episodes (332 with outcome data), 271 (81.6%; 95% CI 77.1–85.4) reported meaningful improvement within three days, including 122 (36.7%) within 24 hours. One respondent (0.3%) reported no improvement or worsening. When asked the difference the kit made, 172 (51.8%; 46.4–57.1) selected “reduced the need for urgent care or the ER,” 115 (34.6%) reduced disruption to daily life, and 31 (9.3%) help managing until care was available. Only 4 (1.2%) reported no meaningful difference. After the episode, 286 (86.1%; 82.0–89.4) sought no in-person care. The remainder saw primary care (37, 11.1%), urgent care (7, 2.1%), or the emergency department (1, 0.3%), and one respondent (0.3%) was hospitalized. Among all use-reporting respondents, 20/368 (5.4%; 3.5–8.2) reported any urgent-care, ED, or hospitalization visit within 7 days of kit use. No work or school days were missed in 213/332 episodes (64.2%). We then combined the three positive response options on the perceived-difference item into a post hoc composite of overall self-reported net benefit. The numerator is the count of intended-use episodes in which the respondent selected any positive option: reduced urgent-care/ED need (172), reduced disruption to work, travel, or daily life (115), or help managing until care was available (31). The denominator is the 332 intended-use episodes with a response to the item. By this definition, 318 of 332 episodes (95.8%; 95% CI 93.0–97.5, Wilson) reported benefit of some degree. The 14 episodes not meeting the composite answered, “not sure” (10) or “no meaningful difference” (4). The perceived-difference item offered no harm option, and one respondent reported no improvement or worsening on the time-to-improvement item. Under the stricter definition, which required a positive perceived difference together with meaningful improvement within 7 days and no reported side effect, 303 of 332 episodes qualified (91.3%; 87.7–93.8). Results were essentially unchanged in the all-episode sensitivity analysis (improvement ≤ 3 days 82.0%; perceived urgent-care/ED reduction 52.7%; any-benefit composite 95.8%) (**Table 4; Figure 3**).

In pre-specified comparisons, neither age group (≥ 60 vs < 60 : 83.5% vs 75.3% improvement ≤ 3 days; $p = 0.14$) nor high symptom severity (72.9% vs 83.1%; $p = 0.14$) was significantly associated with time-to-improvement. Respondents with severe or very severe symptoms sought subsequent in-person care numerically more often (22.9% vs 12.3%; $p = 0.08$). In the exploratory logistic regression ($n = 332$), no covariate was significantly associated with perceived urgent-care/ED substitution (age ≥ 60 : OR 1.47, 95% CI 0.88–2.46; high severity: OR 1.12, 0.61–2.09; respiratory condition: OR 1.00, 0.64–1.55; guidebook read-most: OR 1.17, 0.69–1.96).

Table 4. Self-reported outcomes, intended-use episodes ($n = 332$ with outcome data).

Outcome	n (%)	95% CI
Meaningful improvement within 24 hours	122 (36.7%)	31.7–42.1
Meaningful improvement within 3 days	271 (81.6%)	77.1–85.4
Perceived reduced need for urgent care / ED	172 (51.8%)	46.4–57.1
No subsequent in-person care	286 (86.1%)	82.0–89.4
Zero missed work/school days	213 (64.2%)	—
Overall self-reported net benefit, any degree (post hoc composite) ^a	318 (95.8%)	93.0–97.5
Strict net benefit: benefit + improvement ≤ 7 days + no side effect ^a	303 (91.3%)	87.7–93.8
Any side effect (all mild)	8 (2.4%)	1.2–4.7

Care escalation ≤ 7 days (all use-reporting respondents, n=368)	20 (5.4%)	3.5–8.2
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^a Net-benefit composite: any positive option on the perceived-difference item; post hoc and perception-based. Sensitivity analysis on all medication episodes (n = 355): improvement within 3 days 82.0% (77.6–85.6); perceived urgent-care/ED reduction 52.7% (47.5–57.8); any-benefit composite 95.8% (93.1–97.4).

Figure 3. Self-reported outcomes among intended-use episodes. (A) Time to meaningful improvement. (B) Perceived difference made.

3.6 Safety

Among intended-use episodes, 8/332 (2.4%; 95% CI 1.2–4.7) reported any side effect or safety concern. All were classified by respondents as mild, and none led to seeking care (reported concerns: gastrointestinal effects, 4; other/not sure, 3; worsening illness or delayed-care concern, 1). Most respondents reported no deviations from labeled use (297/353, 84.1%). Guidebook engagement was not associated with deviations from labeled use (read most: 43/273, 15.8%, vs skimmed/no: 13/80, 16.3%; $p = 1.0$) (Table 5).

Table 5. Safety findings.

Item	n/N (%)	95% CI
Any side effect, intended-use episodes (all mild)	8/332 (2.4%)	1.2–4.7
Any use outside labeled directions	56/353 (15.9%)	12.4–20.0

3.7 Free-text findings

Open-text comments were left by 360/506 respondents (71.1%). Theme frequencies are shown in **Table 6**. The dominant themes were peace of mind/reassurance (60, 16.7% of commenters), general gratitude or endorsement (66, 18.3%), travel and remote-setting relevance (46, 12.8%), and preparedness motivations (51, 14.2%). Positive experience themes dominated the corpus, and constructive feedback concentrated on product logistics such as refills and expiration dating rather than on product performance. Perceived-impact statements coded only where explicit included avoidance of a clinic, urgent-care, or ED visit (14, 3.9%), access when conventional care was unavailable or delayed (9, 2.5%), perceived rapid recovery (6, 1.7%), and perceived cost avoidance (6, 1.7%). Four commenters (1.1%) used colloquial “lifesaver” language, and no comment described a literal life-threatening event averted. Constructive feedback converged with the structured findings: expiration-dating concerns (22, 6.1%), refill and price friction (34, 9.4%), requests for broader medication coverage (3), and indication/dosing uncertainty (3). As a consistency check, of the 14 commenters spontaneously describing visit avoidance, 13 had described a structured episode and 9 had also selected the structured “reduced need for urgent care or the ER” option.

Table 6. Free-text themes (n = 360 commenters).

Theme	n (%)	Illustrative quote
General gratitude / endorsement	66 (18.3%)	“Thank you for a great product!”
Peace of mind / reassurance	60 (16.7%)	“It affords me peace of mind... and when traveling.”
Preparedness motivation	51 (14.2%)	“When medicine is restricted or extremely limited, I am prepared.”
Travel / remote-setting relevance	46 (12.8%)	“I take this kit... with me everywhere.”
Refill / price friction	34 (9.4%)	“The refills are too expensive.”
Expiration-dating concerns	22 (6.1%)	“I expected them to expire a lot later.”
Perceived visit avoidance (explicit)	14 (3.9%)	“It was convenient and saved us a trip to urgent care.”
Access when care unavailable/delayed	9 (2.5%)	“Care was not available at that time so I used a Rx from the kit.”
Perceived rapid recovery	6 (1.7%)	“Peace of mind! Quick relief of symptoms.”
Perceived cost avoidance	6 (1.7%)	“I know my symptoms and can’t always afford urgent care.”
Colloquial “lifesaver” language	4 (1.1%)	“This has been a life saver.”
Autonomy / self-reliance	10 (2.8%)	“I am prepared to take care of myself.”
Indication/dosing uncertainty	3 (0.8%)	“I am not sure of what each medication... [treats].”

Requests for broader coverage	3 (0.8%)	“More standard antibiotics... included in the kit.”
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Counts reflect explicit statements only; quotes lightly edited for length and screened for identifying detail.

3.8 Satisfaction, preparedness, and exploratory cost-offset scenarios

Advocacy and preparedness measures were strongly favorable. The Net Promoter Score was 74.7 (bootstrap 95% CI 70.0–79.6), with 81.0% of respondents classified as promoters and 6.3% as detractors. Owning the kit improved peace of mind “a lot” for 406 respondents (80.2%), and 419 (82.8%) felt much more prepared for situations in which access to care is limited. These benefits did not depend on use: among the 139 respondents who had never used the kit, 87 (62.6%) reported “a lot” of peace-of-mind benefit and 95 (68.3%) felt much more prepared, a pattern consistent with an insurance-like value model in which readiness itself is the benefit for a substantial minority of owners. Repurchase intent was correspondingly high (definitely, 327, 64.6%; probably, 124, 24.5%).

Exploratory cost-offset scenarios (perception-based; illustrative only). If respondent perceptions of avoided visits are taken at face value, the 172 intended-use episodes reporting a reduced need for urgent care or the ED imply per-episode offsets ranging from \$165–220 if all avoided visits are valued as urgent-care visits (published mean urgent-care price \$220 in 2022 [19]; payer-reported median \$165 [20]), \$82–110 under a discounted scenario assuming half of perceived-avoided episodes would have required no paid care (reflecting the self-limiting course of much acute respiratory illness), and \$391–438 under an upper-bound scenario in which the 14.7% of episodes rated severe or very severe are valued at a median ED visit (\$1,700 [20]; national mean ED costs and out-of-pocket burdens are of similar order [17,18]). Aggregated across the 172 perceived-avoided episodes in this cohort, the implied offsets total approximately \$14,000–19,000 (scenario B), \$28,000–38,000 (scenario A), and \$67,000–75,000 (scenario C), set against the current kit price of \$299.99 for context only. Perceptions of avoided care cannot be verified, some episodes may have required no paid care, and no comparison group exists. These scenarios are therefore illustrative and are not carried into the conclusions (**Table 7**).

Table 7. Exploratory cost-offset scenarios (perception-based).

Scenario	Assumption	Per-episode offset	Cohort aggregate (172 episodes)
A. All perceived-avoided visits are urgent care	100% urgent care	\$165–220	\$28,400–37,800
B. Discounted: half required no paid care	50% × Scenario A	\$82–110	\$14,100–18,900
C. Severity-weighted ED share	14.7% ED, remainder urgent care	\$391–438	\$67,300–75,300

Anchored to 172 episodes with perceived urgent-care/ED reduction. Benchmarks: references [17–20]. Kit retail price \$299.99.

3.9 Rural–urban comparisons

Among the 486 respondents with classifiable ZIP codes, non-metropolitan respondents used the kit numerically more often than metropolitan respondents (95/121, 78.5%, vs 254/365, 69.6%; $p = 0.076$), but perceived urgent-care/ED substitution did not differ (48/88, 54.5%, vs 118/230, 51.3%; $p = 0.70$), and travel/remote use did not differ by rurality ($p = 0.66$).

4. Discussion

In this survey of 506 verified purchasers of a DTC prescribed emergency medication kit, we found near-universal product engagement, kit use by 72% of respondents (concentrated in respiratory and urinary illness), rapid self-reported symptom resolution, a perceived reduction in urgent-care or ED need in half of intended-use episodes (with self-reported benefit of some degree in 96%), a low rate of side effects, and a favorable appropriate-use profile. To our knowledge these are the first published real-world utilization data for this product category.

The potential for cost savings and reductions in morbidity and mortality are important considerations. For many acute medical conditions, earlier initiation of appropriate treatment is associated with improved clinical outcomes and reduced morbidity and mortality [1-3]. Convenience and timely access to care are also important factors. A peer-reviewed study of the urgent care literature found that wait times at urgent care centers typically ranged from 22.5 to 55 minutes, whereas emergency department wait times ranged from 2.5 to 17 hours, depending on location and crowding. [21]

The utilization picture aligns with the access rationale for standby treatment. The respondent population skewed older (77% aged ≥ 60), and although three-quarters resided in metropolitan ZIP codes, participants from non-metropolitan areas were well represented and trended toward higher kit utilization. Episodes clustered around situations in which conventional access is most strained: weekends, holidays, appointment delays, and travel, with a fifth of episodes occurring away from home and 31% of users reporting travel or remote use. The same pattern surfaced repeatedly in the free-text comments. The predominant first action, consulting the guidebook (67%), suggests the kit functions for most users as a guided self-care pathway rather than unstructured self-medication, and is consistent with the written self-treatment guidance long recommended in travel medicine for standby therapy [9,10].

The safety and self-management profile observed here is reassuring. Side effects were uncommon (2.4%) and uniformly mild, only 5.4% of use-reporting respondents had a care-escalation visit within a week of kit use, and 86% of intended-use episodes resolved without any subsequent in-person care. Use was guided rather than improvised: two thirds of users consulted the guidebook before acting, mirroring the written self-treatment instructions that are a guideline-endorsed component of standby therapy in travel medicine [9,10]. Combined with meaningful improvement within three days in more than four of five episodes and self-reported benefit of some degree in 96%, these findings indicate that the kit functioned largely as designed in this population. It provided a structured, pre-prescribed pathway—medications prescribed prophylactically for use at the onset of illness—for managing common acute illness at home, at the times and in the places where conventional access is least practical.

Appropriate-use indicators were likewise favorable. More than four of five respondents (81.8%) correctly identified that the kit is intended for the prescribed recipient alone, 93.5% of medication episodes involved the prescribed recipient, and 84% of users reported no deviations from labeled use. The prescribing model builds in safeguards before the kit ever reaches the home, including medical-history review with allergy-based substitution at the point of prescribing and an individually prescribed kit for each adult in multi-user households. The deviation rates observed sit within the lower portion of the broad

prevalence ranges reported for prescription medication sharing in general populations, where lending spans 6–23% and borrowing 5–52% [22,23]. Respondent feedback identified extended expiration dating as the most requested enhancement, and federal shelf-life extension data showing that many solid oral products remain stable well beyond labeled dates when properly stored [24] suggest this is a tractable opportunity for the product category.

Advocacy and preparedness metrics were exceptionally strong and value accrued even among never-users, two-thirds of whom reported substantial peace-of-mind benefit, consistent with an insurance-like value model for this product category. The exploratory cost-offset scenarios suggest that, under face-value assumptions, perceived avoided visits are of the same order as the kit price, though these scenarios are perception-based and illustrative. The rigorous test of the economic question is a claims-linked utilization study comparing actual care utilization before and after kit purchase, which these results motivate. Such a study could also value the full economic burden these kits may offset, which extends beyond the visit charge itself to the time patients spend traveling to and waiting at urgent care or emergency departments, the time awaiting prescriptions, and the value of work and other activities not missed when illness is managed promptly at home. Modeling the customary care-seeking behavior of U.S. patients—many of whom default to urgent care or the emergency department for common acute illness—against the kit-enabled alternative would help quantify these convenience and productivity components, and represents a distinct study implied by these findings. Beyond direct visit charges, conventional care for minor acute illness imposes substantial time and experiential costs: the median emergency department visit in the United States lasts roughly 2 hours and 40 minutes [25], and obtaining treatment typically requires travel, waiting, and a separate trip to a pharmacy before the first dose is taken. These burdens are not merely inconvenient. Survey data indicate that a meaningful share of adults delay or forgo needed care because of its cost and difficulty, and that among those who do, a substantial proportion report that their health subsequently worsened [26]. By placing a clinician-reviewed course of treatment in the home before illness begins, pre-prescribed kits are positioned to lower precisely these barriers—cost at the point of need, travel and waiting time, and the friction of pharmacy access—and thereby to support earlier treatment in exactly the situations where delay is most consequential. Whether this translates into measurable reductions in care avoidance and downstream morbidity is a question these data motivate rather than resolve.

Strengths of this study include its use of a verified purchaser sampling frame with a delivered-invitation denominator, allowing the response fraction to be calculated directly and responders to be compared with the broader customer frame. To our knowledge, this is the first real-world utilization dataset for direct-to-consumer prescribed emergency medication kits, capturing not only ownership and engagement but also episode-level use, symptom category, first actions taken, medication selection, perceived outcomes, subsequent care-seeking, side effects, and use outside labeled directions. The analysis also incorporated a frame-wide non-response assessment showing demographic similarity between responders and non-responders on sex, geography, and rurality, with only modest age imbalance. Additional strengths include complete reporting of item-specific denominators, prespecified appropriate-use and deviation measures, Wilson confidence intervals for key proportions, sensitivity analyses, and convergence between structured responses and free-text comments. Together, these features provide a transparent and clinically

informative first assessment of how a pre-prescribed standby medication kit is used in real-world household, travel, and remote-access settings.

5. Limitations

Several limitations should inform interpretation of these findings. First, respondents were self-selected customers of a single commercial product. The results therefore describe the experiences of this customer population and should not be assumed to generalize to the broader public. Although responders closely resembled the customer frame demographically, satisfied users may still have been more likely to participate. Second, the response fraction was low (9.2%). While the frame-wide non-response analysis reduces concern about major demographic bias, it cannot eliminate selection effects, particularly because responders were modestly older than non-responders (SMD 0.23). Third, all diagnoses, outcomes, and perceptions of avoided care were self-reported and unverified. No medical-record review, claims confirmation, or comparison group was available, meaning that perceived reductions in urgent care or emergency department use should not be interpreted as demonstrated clinical effectiveness. Relatedly, the survey could not distinguish bacterial from viral illness. Because many acute illnesses are self-limited, reported improvement may reflect effective treatment, natural recovery, or both. Finally, recall windows extended beyond one year for approximately 10% of episodes, introducing the possibility of recall bias. Because the response fraction was low, responders may not fully represent all kit purchasers; the frame-wide comparison on age, sex, state, and rurality (**Supplementary Table 1**) showed closely similar distributions, supporting representativeness of the analytic sample on measured characteristics.

6. Conclusion

To our knowledge, this study provides the first real-world evidence on how direct-to-consumer prescribed emergency medication kits are actually used, and the picture that emerges is a positive one. Engagement was near universal. Customers used their kits frequently for common acute illness, often at the times and in the places where conventional access and timely receipt of medication are most strained. They reported rapid recovery with few and uniformly mild side effects and benefit of some degree in 96% of intended-use episodes. The appropriate-use profile was favorable, with deviation rates in the lower portion of published general-population medication-sharing ranges, and preparedness and peace-of-mind value extended even to owners who never opened a medication. Our findings indicate that pre-prescribed medication kits can function as a structured, well-received, and largely appropriately used approach—providing essential medications prescribed prophylactically—to managing common acute illness outside conventional care settings. Medical emergency kits work to bridge the gap between the aspiration of guidelines (e.g., reduced time to first antimicrobial administration) and actual clinical effectiveness. As access barriers, travel-related care gaps, and household preparedness concerns continue to grow, emergency medication kits may represent a scalable and clinically practical model for improving timely access to treatment worthy of prospective evaluation. Large prospective, randomized trials are warranted in willing populations at risk for common illnesses covered in the kits.

Independent Institutional Ethics Committee Statement: This study was a retrospective analysis of de-identified data derived from questionnaires voluntarily and anonymously completed by clients (voluntary, anonymous, patient-reported data). Institutional Review Board (IRB) review was not required because the study involved the analysis of existing, de-identified data and did not involve direct interaction with participants. Participants provided consent through the questionnaire for the use and publication of their anonymized data. The study was conducted in accordance with applicable ethical standards for research involving human data.

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Nicolas Hulscher, MPH: Conceptualization; Methodology; Formal analysis; Data curation; Visualization; Writing – original draft; Writing – review & editing; Supervision.

Kelly Victory, MD: Conceptualization; Supervision; Methodology; Writing – original draft; Writing – review & editing.

James A. Thorp, MD: Conceptualization; Writing – original draft; Writing – review & editing.

Drew Pinsky, MD: Conceptualization; Writing – original draft; Writing – review & editing.

Peter Gillooly, MSc: Conceptualization; Data curation; Formal analysis; Writing – original draft; Writing – review & editing.

Foster Coulson: Investigation; Project administration; Writing – original draft; Writing – review & editing.

Melissa Annazone: Investigation; Data curation; Writing – original draft; Writing – review & editing.

Chloe Radesi: Investigation; Data curation; Writing – original draft; Writing – review & editing.

Jessica Brooks: Investigation; Project administration; Writing – original draft; Writing – review & editing.

Peter A. McCullough, MD, MPH: Conceptualization; Supervision; Writing – original draft; Writing – review & editing.

Harvey Risch, MD, PhD: Conceptualization; Methodology; Formal analysis; Supervision; Writing – original draft; Writing – review & editing.

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Supplementary Material

Supplementary Table 1. Comparison of survey responders and the full customer frame on available characteristics.

Characteristic	Responders (n = 523)	Non-responders (n = 5,859)	p value
Age, mean (SD), years	65.1 (10.5)	62.4 (12.4)	<0.001 ^a
Age ≥60 years, n (%)	400 (76.5)	3,837 (65.5)	<0.001
Female sex, n (%)	300 (57.4)	3,241 (55.3)	0.39
Non-metropolitan residence, n (%) ^b	126 (25.1)	1,397 (24.2)	0.71
State distribution	—	—	0.056 ^c

Responder counts reflect frame records matched to survey respondents by email; a small number of household-shared addresses match multiple adult records, so the responder record count modestly exceeds 506. Standardized mean difference for age = 0.23. ^aMann-Whitney U statistic. ^bAmong records with classifiable ZIP codes (RUCRA approximation). ^cChi-square statistic across the eight most frequent states plus an “other” category. Income, education, and clinical characteristics were not captured in the customer frame and could not be compared.